

AlloDyn: Integrating Molecular Dynamics and Generative Conformational Ensembles for Allosteric Site Prediction

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Supplementary

Tables

Table S1: Benchmarking set (D24)

PDB ID	Modulator ID	Chain	Modulator Residue No.
1MC0	PCG	A	160
4OYA	1VE	A	501
2CDQ	SAM	A	1500
1WQW	BT5	A	1301
5J94	1XF	A	301
4PCU	SAM	A	603
4NHV	2O6	A	308
2XEM	SSV	B	1145
4DQW	ATP	A	503
4TPT	35H	A	701
4FXV	0W2	P	701
3ZFZ	1W8	A	1669
3ZFZ	MUR	B	1669
4PPV	PHE	A	401
5BTR	STL	A	702
2C2B	SAM*	A	501
4QPL	V3L	A	201
4ZLO	4PV	A	601
5CGC	51D	A	4006
4YW8	1WD	A	708
5DE1	59D	A	502
5C4T	4Y6	A	601
3UVV	9CR	B	501
5DED	0O2	A	302

*Allosteric modulator (SAM) is located in chain B of the asymmetric dimer.

Table S2: Comparison of fpocket descriptors between biased and unbiased configurations. Biased: *fpocket* applied directly to the holo structure without prior structure preparation. Unbiased: *fpocket* applied after structure preparation, with the allosteric modulator removed from the chain. For 1MC0, the biased configuration corresponds to Pocket 1 and the unbiased configuration to Pocket 7. For 1F1O, both configurations correspond to Pocket 1.

Feature	1MC0		3F1O	
	Biased	Unbiased	Biased	Unbiased
Score	0.358	0.014	0.937	0.630
Druggability score	0.069	0.037	0.860	0.839
Number of alpha spheres	50	50	85	85
Total SASA	53.627	138.792	1.208	76.956
Polar SASA	24.644	57.881	0.000	8.616
Apolar SASA	28.983	80.911	1.208	68.340
Volume	446.241	454.061	405.616	408.810
Mean local hydrophobic density	20.273	20.273	38.453	38.453
Mean alpha sphere radius	3.852	3.852	3.768	3.768
Mean alpha sphere solvent accessibility	0.424	0.424	0.470	0.470
Apolar alpha sphere proportion	0.440	0.440	0.624	0.624
Hydrophobicity score	46.200	46.200	49.682	49.682
Volume score	4.467	4.467	4.182	4.182
Polarity score	7	7	9	9
Charge score	-3	-3	2	2
Proportion of polar atoms	31.429	31.429	31.250	31.250
Alpha sphere density	4.382	4.382	4.958	4.958
Center of mass-alpha sphere max distance	11.266	11.266	10.556	10.556
Flexibility	0.232	0.232	0.092	0.092

Table S3: Model performance on biased and unbiased datasets, averaged over 50 random seeds. For each dataset, results are reported for the *fpocket*-only baseline and AlloDyn models augmented with MD- or AlphaFlow-derived dynamic features. Values are reported as mean \pm standard deviation of test set performance across the 50 splits.

Source	Model	Precision	Recall	F1	MCC	AUC ROC	AUC PR
Biased	Baseline	0.57 \pm 0.05	0.65 \pm 0.09	0.60 \pm 0.05	0.59 \pm 0.05	0.94 \pm 0.02	0.61 \pm 0.06
	AlloDyn (Fpocket+MD)	0.54 \pm 0.03	0.69 \pm 0.09	0.61 \pm 0.04	0.59 \pm 0.05	0.95 \pm 0.01	0.59 \pm 0.04
	AlloDyn (Fpocket+AlphaFlow)	0.56 \pm 0.05	0.68 \pm 0.08	0.61 \pm 0.05	0.60 \pm 0.05	0.95 \pm 0.02	0.62 \pm 0.05
Unbiased	Baseline	0.46 \pm 0.06	0.41 \pm 0.06	0.43 \pm 0.05	0.41 \pm 0.05	0.86 \pm 0.03	0.40 \pm 0.06
	AlloDyn (Fpocket+MD)	0.48 \pm 0.06	0.42 \pm 0.05	0.45 \pm 0.05	0.43 \pm 0.05	0.86 \pm 0.02	0.41 \pm 0.06
	AlloDyn (Fpocket+AlphaFlow)	0.48 \pm 0.06	0.42 \pm 0.06	0.45 \pm 0.05	0.43 \pm 0.05	0.87 \pm 0.02	0.40 \pm 0.06

Table S4: Features used for allosteric pocket prediction. Features are grouped into five categories: fpocket structural descriptors, MD-derived dynamics features, SASA-based features, intra-pocket residue correlation features, and pocket-to-pocket correlation features. Correlation features are computed from four matrices: Generalized Correlation (GC) and Mutual Information (MI) from COMPASS-GC, Communication Propensity (COMMPROP) from COMPASS-GC, and Pearson correlation derived from MD trajectories. In symbols, * denotes one of {gc, mi, commprop, pearson} unless stated otherwise.

Feature	Symbol	Description
<i>fpocket structural features</i>		
Pocket score	fp_1	Overall pocket score computed by fpocket
Druggability score	fp_2	Predicted druggability of the pocket
Number of alpha spheres	fp_3	Count of alpha spheres defining the pocket
Total SASA	fp_4	Total solvent accessible surface area (\AA^2)
Polar SASA	fp_5	Polar solvent accessible surface area (\AA^2)
Apolar SASA	fp_6	Apolar solvent accessible surface area (\AA^2)
Volume	fp_7	Pocket volume (\AA^3)
Mean local hydrophobic density	fp_8	Average hydrophobic density around alpha spheres
Mean alpha sphere radius	fp_9	Average radius of alpha spheres (\AA)
Mean alpha sphere solvent access	fp_10	Average solvent accessibility of alpha spheres
Apolar alpha sphere proportion	fp_11	Fraction of apolar alpha spheres
Hydrophobicity score	fp_12	Pocket hydrophobicity score
Volume score	fp_13	Normalized volume score
Polarity score	fp_14	Pocket polarity score
Charge score	fp_15	Net charge score of the pocket
Proportion of polar atoms	fp_16	Fraction of polar atoms in the pocket
Alpha sphere density	fp_17	Density of alpha spheres in the pocket
Alpha sphere max distance	fp_18	Maximum distance from center of mass to alpha spheres (\AA)
Flexibility	fp_19	Pocket flexibility score based on B-factors
<i>MD-derived dynamics features</i>		
Centroid std	centroid_std	Standard deviation of pocket centroid position across trajectory (\AA)
Radius of gyration mean	rg_mean	Mean radius of gyration of pocket residues (\AA)
Radius of gyration std	rg_std	Standard deviation of radius of gyration (\AA)
Min distance to centroid mean	cent_min_dist_mean	Mean of minimum residue-to-centroid distances (\AA)
Min distance to centroid std	cent_min_dist_std	Std of minimum residue-to-centroid distances (\AA)

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Feature	Symbol	Description
Avg distance to centroid mean	cent_avg_dist_mean	Mean of average residue-to-centroid distances (Å)
Avg distance to centroid std	cent_avg_dist_std	Std of average residue-to-centroid distances (Å)
Max distance to centroid mean	cent_max_dist_mean	Mean of maximum residue-to-centroid distances (Å)
Max distance to centroid std	cent_max_dist_std	Std of maximum residue-to-centroid distances (Å)
Inter-residue distance mean	interres_avg_dist_mean	Mean of average pairwise inter-residue distances (Å)
Inter-residue distance std	interres_avg_dist_std	Std of average pairwise inter-residue distances (Å)
RMSF mean	rmsf_mean	Mean root mean square fluctuation of C α atoms (Å)
RMSF std	rmsf_std	Standard deviation of RMSF values (Å)
Anisotropy mean	anisotropy_mean	Mean shape anisotropy from PCA eigenvalues
Anisotropy std	anisotropy_std	Standard deviation of anisotropy
Sphericity mean	sphericity_mean	Mean sphericity from PCA eigenvalues
Sphericity std	sphericity_std	Standard deviation of sphericity
<i>SASA-based features</i>		
SASA mean (absolute)	sasa_mean_abs	Mean pocket SASA across ensemble (Å ²)
SASA std (absolute)	sasa_std_abs	Standard deviation of pocket SASA (Å ²)
SASA range (absolute)	sasa_range_abs	Range of pocket SASA values (Å ²)
SASA CV (absolute)	sasa_cv_abs	Coefficient of variation of pocket SASA
SASA mean (relative)	sasa_mean_rel	Mean pocket SASA relative to total protein SASA
SASA std (relative)	sasa_std_rel	Std of relative pocket SASA
SASA range (relative)	sasa_range_rel	Range of relative pocket SASA
SASA CV (relative)	sasa_cv_rel	Coefficient of variation of relative pocket SASA
<i>Intra-pocket residue correlation features</i>		
Number of pocket residues (corr.)	n_pocket_residues_corr	Number of pocket residues mapped to the correlation matrix
Intra-pocket correlation mean	*_intra_mean	Mean pairwise correlation between all pocket residue pairs; computed for GC, MI, COMMPROP, and Pearson
Intra-pocket correlation max	*_intra_max	Maximum pairwise intra-pocket correlation
Intra-pocket correlation std	*_intra_std	Standard deviation of pairwise intra-pocket correlations

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Feature	Symbol	Description
High intra-pocket correlation fraction	gc_high_corr_frac, pearson_high_corr_frac	Fraction of intra-pocket residue pairs with $ \text{corr} > 0.5$ (GC and Pearson only)
Intra-pocket Pearson min	pearson_intra_min	Minimum pairwise Pearson correlation within the pocket
Intra-pocket Pearson absolute mean	pearson_intra_abs_mean	Mean $ r $ between pocket residue pairs
Intra-pocket Pearson absolute max	pearson_intra_abs_max	Maximum $ r $ within the pocket
Intra-pocket Pearson absolute std	pearson_intra_abs_std	Standard deviation of $ r $ within the pocket
Intra-pocket positive correlation fraction	pearson_intra_pos_frac	Fraction of intra-pocket pairs with $r > 0$
Intra-pocket negative correlation fraction	pearson_intra_neg_frac	Fraction of intra-pocket pairs with $r < 0$
<i>Global connectivity features (pocket to rest of protein)</i>		
Global connectivity mean	*_global_mean	Mean correlation between pocket residues and all non-pocket protein residues; computed for GC, MI, COMMPROP, and Pearson
Global connectivity std	*_global_std	Standard deviation of pocket-to-rest correlations
Global Pearson absolute mean	pearson_global_abs_mean	Mean $ r $ between pocket and remaining protein residues
Global Pearson absolute std	pearson_global_abs_std	Standard deviation of $ r $ for pocket-to-rest pairs
Global positive correlation fraction	pearson_global_pos_frac	Fraction of pocket-to-rest pairs with $r > 0$
Global negative correlation fraction	pearson_global_neg_frac	Fraction of pocket-to-rest pairs with $r < 0$
<i>Pocket-to-pocket correlation features</i>		
Number of other pockets	n_other_pockets	Number of other fpocket pockets detected in the same protein
Inter-pocket correlation mean	*_to_other_pockets_mean	Mean of per-pocket average correlations between this pocket and each other pocket; computed for GC, MI, COMMPROP, and Pearson
Inter-pocket correlation max	*_to_other_pockets_max	Maximum per-pocket mean correlation (most correlated other pocket)
Inter-pocket correlation min	*_to_other_pockets_min	Minimum per-pocket mean correlation (least correlated other pocket)
Inter-pocket correlation std	*_to_other_pockets_std	Standard deviation of per-pocket mean correlations
Max residue-pair correlation	*_max_pocket_pair_corr	Maximum single residue-pair correlation across all inter-pocket pairs

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Feature	Symbol	Description
Number of highly correlated pockets	*n_high_corr_pockets	Number of other pockets with mean correlation above threshold (> 0.3 for Pearson/GC; > 0.2 for MI/COMMPROP)
Inter-pocket Pearson absolute mean	pearson_to_other_pockets_abs_mean	Mean absolute Pearson correlation to residues of other pockets
Inter-pocket Pearson absolute max	pearson_to_other_pockets_abs_max	Maximum absolute mean Pearson correlation to any other pocket
Inter-pocket Pearson absolute std	pearson_to_other_pockets_abs_std	Standard deviation of absolute mean Pearson correlations across other pockets
Inter-pocket positive correlation fraction	pearson_to_other_pockets_pos_frac	Fraction of inter-pocket residue pairs with $r > 0$
Inter-pocket negative correlation fraction	pearson_to_other_pockets_neg_frac	Fraction of inter-pocket residue pairs with $r < 0$
Max absolute residue-pair correlation	pearson_max_pocket_pair_abs_corr	Maximum $ r $ for any single inter-pocket residue pair

Table S5: Non-fpocket features: MD-derived dynamics, SASA, and residue-residue correlation descriptors with calculation methods. Dynamics and SASA features are computed from MD trajectories using MDAnalysis and MDTraj ($C\alpha$ atoms of pocket-lining residues). Correlation features are derived from four $N \times N$ residue-residue matrices: Generalized Correlation (GC) and Mutual Information (MI) from COMPASS-GC, Communication Propensity (COMMPROP) from COMPASS-GC, and Pearson correlation (r) computed from $C\alpha$ positional time series. In feature names, * denotes one of {gc, mi, commprop, pearson}. $I_{\mathcal{P}}$ denotes the set of 0-indexed residue indices mapped to the pocket; $\bar{I}_{\mathcal{P}} = \{0, \dots, N-1\} \setminus I_{\mathcal{P}}$ is the complement.

Feature	Formula	Description
<i>Pocket geometry features (per-frame, then aggregated)</i>		
centroid_std	$\ \sigma(\mathbf{c}_t)\ $, where $\mathbf{c}_t = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{r}_i^t$	Euclidean norm of standard deviation of pocket centroid position across T frames. Measures overall pocket mobility.
rg_mean, rg_std	$R_g = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{c} ^2}$	Radius of gyration per frame, then mean and std across trajectory. Characterizes pocket compactness.
cent_min_dist_mean, _std	$d_{\min} = \min_i \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{c} $	Minimum $C\alpha$ -to-centroid distance per frame, aggregated as mean and std.
cent_avg_dist_mean, _std	$d_{\text{avg}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{c} $	Average $C\alpha$ -to-centroid distance per frame, aggregated as mean and std.
cent_max_dist_mean, _std	$d_{\max} = \max_i \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{c} $	Maximum $C\alpha$ -to-centroid distance per frame, aggregated as mean and std.
interres_avg_dist_mean, _std	$\bar{d}_{ij} = \frac{2}{N(N-1)} \sum_{i < j} \mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_j $	Mean pairwise $C\alpha$ distance per frame, aggregated as mean and std.
<i>Fluctuation features</i>		

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Feature	Formula	Description
rmsf_mean, rmsf_std	$\text{RMSF}_i = \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \mathbf{r}_i^t - \langle \mathbf{r}_i \rangle ^2}$	Per-residue RMSF computed via MD-Analysis. Mean and std taken across pocket residues.
Shape descriptor features (PCA-based)		
anisotropy_mean, _std	$A = \frac{\lambda_3}{\lambda_1}$, where $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \lambda_3$	Ratio of smallest to largest PCA eigenvalue per frame. $A \rightarrow 0$: elongated; $A \rightarrow 1$: isotropic.
sphericity_mean, _std	$S = \frac{(\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3)^{1/3}}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3}$	Geometric mean of eigenvalues normalized by their sum per frame. Higher values indicate more spherical shape.
SASA-based features		
sasa_mean_abs	$\bar{A} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T A_{\text{pocket}}^t$	Mean pocket SASA across trajectory (\AA^2).
sasa_std_abs	$\sigma_A = \sqrt{\frac{1}{T-1} \sum_{t=1}^T (A^t - \bar{A})^2}$	Standard deviation of pocket SASA (\AA^2).
sasa_range_abs	$\Delta A = A_{\text{max}} - A_{\text{min}}$	Range of pocket SASA values (\AA^2).
sasa_cv_abs	$\text{CV} = \frac{\sigma_A}{\bar{A}}$	Coefficient of variation of pocket SASA.
sasa_mean_rel	$\bar{A}_{\text{rel}} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{A_{\text{pocket}}^t}{A_{\text{total}}^t}$	Mean fraction of pocket SASA relative to total protein SASA per frame.
sasa_std_rel	$\sigma_{A_{\text{rel}}}$	Standard deviation of relative SASA.
sasa_range_rel	$\Delta A_{\text{rel}} = A_{\text{rel,max}} - A_{\text{rel,min}}$	Range of relative SASA values.
sasa_cv_rel	$\text{CV}_{\text{rel}} = \frac{\sigma_{A_{\text{rel}}}}{A_{\text{rel}}}$	Coefficient of variation of relative pocket SASA.
Intra-pocket residue correlation features		
n_pocket_residues_corr	$ I_{\mathcal{P}} $	Number of pocket residues mapped to the correlation matrix.
_intra_mean, _max, _std	$V = \{C_{ij}^ : i, j \in I_{\mathcal{P}}, i < j\}$; $\text{mean}(V), \text{max}(V), \text{std}(V)$	Mean, max, and std of upper-triangular intra-pocket correlations. Computed for GC, MI, COMMPROP, and Pearson.
gc_high_corr_frac, pearson_high_corr_frac	$\frac{ \{v \in V : v > 0.5\} }{ V }$	Fraction of intra-pocket pairs with $ C_{ij} > 0.5$. Computed for GC and Pearson only.
pearson_intra_min	$\min(V)$	Minimum intra-pocket Pearson correlation.
pearson_intra_abs_mean, _abs_max, _abs_std	$\text{mean}(V), \text{max}(V), \text{std}(V)$	Mean, max, and std of absolute intra-pocket Pearson correlations.

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Feature	Formula	Description
pearson_intra_pos_frac, pearson_intra_neg_frac	$\frac{ \{v \in V : v > 0\} }{ V },$ $\frac{ \{v \in V : v < 0\} }{ V }$	Fraction of intra-pocket pairs with positive / negative Pearson correlation.
Global connectivity features (pocket to rest of protein)		
_global_mean, _global_std	$W = \{C_{ij}^ : i \in I_{\mathcal{P}}, j \in \bar{I}_{\mathcal{P}}\};$ mean(W), std(W)	Mean and std of correlations between pocket and non-pocket residues. Computed for all four matrix types.
pearson_global_abs_mean, pearson_global_abs_std	mean($ W $), std($ W $)	Mean and std of absolute pocket-to-rest Pearson correlations.
pearson_global_pos_frac, pearson_global_neg_frac	$\frac{ \{w \in W : w > 0\} }{ W },$ $\frac{ \{w \in W : w < 0\} }{ W }$	Fraction of pocket-to-rest pairs with positive / negative Pearson correlation.
Pocket-to-pocket correlation features		
n_other_pockets	$K - 1$	Number of other fpocket pockets in the same protein ($K =$ total pocket count).
_to_other_pockets_mean, _max, _min, _std	$\mu_k = \text{mean}_{i \in I_{\mathcal{P}}, j \in I_k} C_{ij}^;$ mean $_k(\mu_k)$, max $_k(\mu_k)$, min $_k(\mu_k)$, std $_k(\mu_k)$	Per-pocket mean correlation μ_k to each other pocket k , then mean, max, min, std across all $K - 1$ pockets. Computed for all four matrix types.
_max_pocket_pair_corr	max $_k \max_{i \in I_{\mathcal{P}}, j \in I_k} C_{ij}^$	Maximum single residue-pair correlation across all inter-pocket pairs.
*_n_high_corr_pockets	$ \{k : \mu_k > \theta\} $	Number of other pockets with mean correlation above threshold. $\theta = 0.3$ for Pearson/GC; $\theta = 0.2$ for MI/COMMPROP.
pearson_to_other_pockets _abs_mean, _abs_max, _abs_std	$ \mu_k ^{\text{abs}} = \text{mean}_{i,j} C_{ij} ;$ mean $_k$, max $_k$, std $_k$ of $ \mu_k ^{\text{abs}}$	Absolute mean Pearson correlation to each other pocket, then mean, max, std across pockets.
pearson_to_other_pockets _pos_frac, _neg_frac	$V_{\text{inter}} = \{C_{ij} : i \in I_{\mathcal{P}}, j \in \bigcup_k I_k\};$ $\frac{ \{v > 0\} }{ V_{\text{inter}} }, \frac{ \{v < 0\} }{ V_{\text{inter}} }$	Fraction of all inter-pocket residue pair correlations that are positive / negative.
pearson_max_pocket_pair _abs_corr	max $_k \max_{i \in I_{\mathcal{P}}, j \in I_k} C_{ij} $	Maximum absolute Pearson correlation for any single inter-pocket residue pair.

Figures

Figure S1: Kernel density estimates of fpocket descriptors. Left: Fpocket score. Right: Druggability score. Solid lines correspond to the biased dataset and dashed lines to the unbiased dataset. Blue curves denote non-allosteric pockets, and red curves denote allosteric pockets.

Figure S2: Predicted allosteric pockets on the D24 benchmark for all evaluated methods (part 1 of 3). Each row corresponds to one D24 entry (PDB ID indicated on the left). Columns show the allosteric site (green, residues within 5 Å of the modulator) and the pockets predicted as positive (allosteric) by each method: AlloDyn (blue), APOP (red), AllosES (magenta), PASSer-AutoML (yellow), PASSer-Ensemble (cyan), and PASSer-Rank (orange). Pockets are displayed as colored surfaces on the protein structure (light blue ribbon). Entries where no pocket is shown indicate that the method failed to return a prediction for that structure.

Figure S3: Predicted allosteric pockets on the D24 benchmark (part 2 of 3). Continued from Fig. S2.

Figure S4: Predicted allosteric pockets on the D24 benchmark (part 3 of 3). Continued from Fig. S3.